

1-(4-Nitrophenyl)-4-phenyl-1*H*-1,2,3-triazole vs 5(6)-nitrobenzofuroxan formation and their antifungal activity

Manvi Jain^a, Maneesh Sharma^a, Manoj Gaur^a, Tara Devi S. Ashok^b, P. Dureja^c and S. V. Eswaran^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, St. Stephen's College, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007, India

E-mail : sv.eswaran@gmail.com

^bDepartment of Biology, University of Massachusetts, Boston, MA, USA

^cDivision of Agricultural Chemicals, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi-110 012, India

Manuscript received 21 January 2010, revised 08 June 2010, accepted 16 July 2010

Abstract : 2,4-Dinitrophenylazide was subjected to 'Click' reaction thermally in the presence of phenyl acetylene and copper sulphate, sodium ascorbate as catalysts. In this reaction instead of the desired 1-(4-nitrophenyl)-4-phenyl-1*H*-1,2,3-triazole, the formation of 5(6)-nitrobenzofuroxan was observed. The same result was obtained when the reaction was carried out in a household microwave oven in 45 s. 'Click' reaction on 4-nitrophenylazide led to the desired triazoles. Thus an intramolecular reaction involving loss of nitrogen (leading to the benzofuroxan formation) occurred in preference to the intermolecular 'Click' reaction. These compounds showed antifungal activity against a pathogenic fungi *Fusarium oxysporum*.

Keywords : Benzofuroxan, 'Click' reaction, intermolecular reaction, intramolecular reaction.

Introduction

The discovery of the 'Click' reaction has led to great excitement not only in chemistry but also in materials science, biochemistry, biology and medicine¹⁻⁷. It is expected to lead to the discovery of new drugs based on *in vivo* affinity based protein profiling (ABPP)⁸. In this paper, a known substituted rapidly equilibrating benzofuroxan and a substituted 1,2,3-triazole have been prepared in a simpler way and characterized spectroscopically. Mass spectrometry has been used to confirm the structures and antifungal activity of these compounds have been evaluated.

Experimental

Chemicals and solvents were purchased from E. Merck or S. D. Fine Chemicals. The reactions were monitored by thin-layer chromatography (TLC) on fluorescent coated plates purchased from E. Merck. Melting points were measured on an electrothermal melting-point apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Spectrum BX series spectrophotometer using KBr. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker 400 MHz. TMS was

used as the internal standard in all cases. MS was recorded using LCQ Ion trap mass spectrometer.

Synthesis of 4-nitrophenylazide (6) :

4-Nitrochlorobenzene (100 mg, 0.63 mmol) was treated with sodium azide (80 mg, 1.2 mmol) in *t*-butanol (3 ml) and heated on a water bath for two hours at 60 °C. Water was added to the reaction mixture and an off white coloured solid obtained was collected by filtration and dried, m.p. 40 °C, yield 60 mg (60%); *R*_f = 0.6 (toluene); IR (KBr) : 3111.90, 2126.69 (N₃), 1593.23, 1515.91, 1490.82 cm⁻¹, ¹H NMR (δ, CDCl₃) : 8.25 (2H, d, Ar-H (3H, 5H), *J*_{ortho} 8.8 Hz), 7.1 (2H, d, Ar-H (2H, 6H), *J*_{ortho} 8.8 Hz).

Synthesis of 1-(4-nitrophenyl)-4-phenyl-1*H*-1,2,3-triazole (4b)⁹ :

To a solution of 4-nitrophenylazide (6) (100 mg, 0.60 mmol) in *t*-butanol : water (3 ml, 3 : 1), phenyl acetylene (100 mg, 1 mmol), catalytic amounts of copper sulphate (0.1 mmol) and sodium ascorbate (0.01 mmol) were added. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 26 h. On adding water to the above solution a buff coloured

solid was obtained, which was collected by filtration and dried, m. p. 230 °C (m.p. not given in the cited literature), yield 150 mg (76%); $R_f = 0.4$ (chloroform); IR (KBr) : 3122.43, 3097.43, 1598.12, 1522.69, 1347.75 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ , CDCl_3) : 7.43 (1H, m), 7.50 (2H, m), 7.97 (2H, d, J_{ortho} 8.0 Hz), 8.07 (2H, d, J_{ortho} 8.0 Hz), 8.30 (1H, s), 8.48 (2H, d, J_{ortho} 8.0 Hz); MS : 266 $[\text{M}]^+$.

Preparation of 5(6)-nitrobenzofuroxan (3) :

2,4-Dinitrochlorobenzene (100 mg, 0.05 mmol) was treated with sodium azide (80 mg, 1.2 mmol) in *t*-butanol : water (3 ml, 3 : 1). The reaction mixture was heated on a water bath (60 °C) for two and half hours to obtain pure 5(6)-nitrobenzofuroxan (3). Water was added to the reaction mixture and the orange-yellow solid obtained was collected by filtration and dried, m.p. 70 °C (lit.¹⁰ 72 °C), yield : 86 mg (86%); $R_f = 0.4$ (toluene); UV spectrum (λ_{max}) : 253.0, 255.2, 326.7, 331.0, 333.2; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ , CDCl_3) : centered at δ 7.65 (1H, br, Ar-H), 8.10 (1H, br, Ar-H), 8.55 (1H, br, Ar-H); MS : 181 $[\text{M}]^+$.

Antifungal activity :

Compounds described in this paper were tested against fungus *Fusarium oxysporum* using disc diffusion assay using hexaconazole as the standard fungicide.

Disc diffusion assay¹¹ : *F. oxysporum* culture (2 ml)

was pipetted on to the surface of the solidified agar plate and spread manually. Excess liquid was removed with a pipette. Six filter paper disks (6 mm) were evenly spaced upon the agar of 10 petri plates, each plate containing standard of hexaconazole. The antifungal solutions were deposited on the disks by use of a 20 μL pipette and plates were incubated at 37 °C for 18 h.

Results and discussion

Our work led to the unexpected formation of 5(6)-nitrobenzofuroxan (3) (this exists in two rapidly equilibrating isomeric forms), viz. 5-nitrobenzofuroxan and 6-nitrobenzofuroxan (Scheme 1), which has been previously described¹². It was formed during an attempted synthesis of 1-(4-nitrophenyl)-1*H*-1,2,3-triazole, using 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene as the starting material. The corresponding intermediate namely 2,4-dinitrophenylazide (2) was generated *in situ*. The results obtained by the conventional method and using a house hold microwave oven were identical, though the latter reaction required only 45 s.

Using 4-nitrochlorobenzene the corresponding azide was synthesised (*ortho* placed nitro group is missing in this case) by aromatic nucleophilic displacement of chlorine. This compound on 'Click' reaction gave the desired triazole (4b) (Scheme 2).

Scheme 1. The formation of rapidly equilibrating 5(6)-nitrobenzofuroxan (3).

Scheme 2. Formation of the expected triazole (4b).

Our study thus provides an example how to direct an intramolecular reaction (benzofuroxan formation) over an intermolecular reaction (1,2,3-triazole formation) pathway. In addition, one learns about aromatic nucleophilic substitution, *in situ* generation of sensitive compounds, and rate acceleration in the microwave oven and especially how to recognize the formation of the unexpected product which exists in two rapidly equilibrating structures.

4-Nitrophenylazide (**6**) was then subjected to 'Click' reaction and 1-(4-nitrophenyl)-4-phenyl-1*H*-1,2,3-triazole (**4b**) was obtained. IR spectrum of compound **4b** showed the absence of 2100 cm⁻¹ peak, indicating the completion of the reaction. The structure of **4b** was further confirmed by its mass spectrum, which showed the molecular ion peak at *m/z* 266 [M]⁺ with base peak at *m/z* 192 and fragment ion peaks at *m/z* 238, 165, 89, 76 (Fig. 1). Fragmentation pattern of the compound is shown in Scheme 3.

Fig. 1. Positive ion EI spectrum of **4b**.

Scheme 3. Mass spectral fragmentation of **4b**.

Antifungal activity :

The above synthesised compounds were tested for antifungal activity and the results are reported in Table 1. In comparison to the antifungal activity of the standard

Table 1. Antifungal activity of compounds

Comps.	Concentration ^a	
	100 ppm	250 ppm
Hexaconazole (standard)	+++++	+++++
4-Nitrophenylazide (6)	+++	+++
5(6)-Benzofuroxan (3)	+++	++++
1-(4-Nitrophenyl)-4-phenyl-1 <i>H</i> -1,2,3-triazole (4b)	++++	+++++

^a + = poor, ++ = moderate, +++ = good, ++++ = very good, +++++ = excellent

hexaconazole, compounds **6** and **3** shows good inhibition at 100 ppm, whereas compound **4b** shows better activity at the same concentration. At 250 ppm activity of **4b** was excellent against *F. oxysporum* followed by compounds **3** and **6**. At 250 ppm the activity of **4b** was found to be excellent and activity comparable to the standard fungicide (Table 1)

Conclusions :

Rate acceleration provided by the *ortho*-nitro group to the intramolecular cyclization of the *in situ* generated azide, leads to the formation of the corresponding benzofuroxan. This reaction thus takes precedence over the intermolecular reaction of this azide with phenyl acetylene in the presence of copper(I). Rate acceleration is also observed in the (house hold) microwave oven. 4-Nitrophenyl azide (**6**), where no *o*-nitro group is present, undergoes the expected 'Click' reaction to form 1-(4-nitrophenyl)-4-phenyl-1*H*-1,2,3-triazole (**4b**). The present work thus allows one to steer the reaction via the intramolecular pathway or the 'Click' route, by changing the reaction conditions appropriately.

Acknowledgement

We thank the Principal, St. Stephen's College, Delhi for providing facilities. We thank CSIR, DRDO, UGC, New Delhi for the grant of research projects, the Director and Dr. Anil Mishra, Head, Cyclotron Division, INMAS, Delhi for NMR studies. Dr. M. Gopal, Division of Agricultural Chemicals, IARI, Pusa and IICT, Hyderabad for GC-MS studies.

References

- H. C. Kolb, M. G. Finn and K. B. Sharpless, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2001, **40**, 2004.
- H. C. Kolb and K. B. Sharpless, *Drug Discovery Today*, 2003, **8**, 1128.

3. W. H. Binder and R. Sachsenhofer, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.*, 2007, **28**, 15.
4. W. H. Binder and C. Kluger, *Curr. Org. Chem.*, 2006, **10**, 1791.
5. S. Prakash, T. M. Long, J. C. Selby, J. S. Moore and M. A. Shannon, *Anal. Chem.*, 2007, **79**, 1661.
6. J. E. Moses and A. D. Moorhouse, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2007, **36**, 1249.
7. H. C. Kolb and K. B. Sharpless, *Drug Discovery Today*, 2003, **8**, 1128.
8. L. V. Lee, M. L. Mitchell, S. J. Huang, V. V. Folkin, K. B. Sharpless and C. H. Wong, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **125**, 9588.
9. K. Barral, A. D. Moorhouse and J. E. Moses, *Org. Lett.*, 2007, **9**, 1809.
10. A. J. Boulton, A. R. Katritzky, M. J. Sewell and B. Wallis, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1967, 914.
11. D. Raahave, *Antimicrobial Agents Chemother.*, 1974, 603.
12. L. I. Vereschagin, F. A. Polkatilov and V. N. Kizhnyayev, *Chem. Heterocycl. Comp.*, 2008, **44**, 1.
13. A. R. Katritzky and M. F. Gordeev, *Heterocycles*, 1993, **35**, 483.